

EDUCATIONAL SERVICES OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract:

The educational process at the university is considered as a process of providing educational services. The main tasks of the educational services market and its regulators are determined. The positions of the subjects of the educational process are indicated and the tasks of the university are formulated to meet their interests in the conditions of a market economy.

Keywords:

Human capital, educational services, characteristics of educational services, educational services market, quality of education, government, employers.

Introduction

Recently, full attention is paid to human capital as a key element in the formation and development of the foundations of the “knowledge-intensive economy” that has emerged in society. In conditions of limited natural resources and the material and financial component of resource potential, it is the reproduction of human capital that becomes the main process determining the effectiveness of socio-economic development.

The dynamics of human capital largely depends on the factors of education, especially higher education. According to the World Bank, the production part of the gross domestic product does not exceed 20 percent, and the rest depends on the quality of human resources. The higher education system is one of the main areas that greatly affects the quality of human capital. In this case, we can consider the process of providing educational services as a reality that takes place in higher educational institutions.

The main part.

The service is specific, but in general, it allows you to use proven mechanisms for analyzing it and subsequently managing its quality. An educational service is understood as an action that helps to acquire systematized knowledge, skills and qualifications.

In our opinion, the essence of the educational services market segment is manifested in the following functions that universities should take into account when organizing these services.

1. Ensuring the balance of quantitative and qualitative indicators between the demand and supply of educational services, while consumers are guided by

the principle of maximizing their well-being in their actions, while producers (universities) strive to maximize their income by minimizing costs.

2. Establishing an objectively balanced market price for educational services.

3. Stimulating the effectiveness of the activities of the university and all its structural divisions in order to find optimal dynamic educational processes for personnel training.

4. Optimizing state orders for the training of specialists with the simultaneous rational use of available material, technical, information, financial resources, as well as professors, teachers and service personnel.

5. Stratifying universities by specialty, taking into account their rating in the field of providing educational services and certification of education quality management systems.

6. Intense competition in the educational services market (which is especially evident at the regional level), forcing universities to use all methods and means to strengthen competition in the market to satisfy the desires of consumers and ensure their well-being.

7. Rationalization of consumption, accompanied by a relative reduction in distribution costs: time and labor spent on obtaining educational services.

The capacity of the educational services market and its segments is constantly changing, as this market is increasingly acquiring the characteristics of an integrated market through the global information space. In addition, the market under consideration enters into systematic interaction with other markets, in which the formation, development and strengthening of human capital, in general, leads to an increase in the resource base of each market, which in turn leads to their quality. This increases the stability of the market and enhances its adaptation to internal and external environmental conditions.

We can list four categories of persons who are most interested in the results of education: the state (representative of the government), employers, the university (representative of teachers) and students (and, for students, their parents). The views of these categories of people on the definition of educational goals and, accordingly, on its quality do not fully coincide [1, 2].

The third subject of consumers of higher education services is individuals who want to get an education. Here the situation is more dynamic. Now the motivation for obtaining higher education has changed somewhat: if earlier higher education provided a more prestigious and well-paid job, now it has become a desire for self-realization in the intellectual sphere or a desire to get a

good salary, as well as entry into the system of work and public administration. Accordingly, students' requirements for the nature of education are changing. First of all, they need to be provided with practical skills, experience in modeling their activities in a team, practical management recommendations, etc.

Students' opinions about the quality of education can be formulated as follows: "The better the conditions for studying at a university for the development of the personality, for satisfying individual needs, the more the university can do to take its rightful place in society, and the higher the quality will be." Although the demand for educational services is formed not only by the quality of education, there is a broader concept of the quality of education at a particular university: this is the quality of the educational institution. A particular consumer can choose an educational institution based on its qualitative characteristics (for example, such a characteristic may be the proximity of the university to the place of residence). The motivation of students (especially junior high school students) is often more focused on the educational process itself and is less influenced by the educational material and the psychological perception of the teacher, the availability of innovative teaching technologies, the convenience of the lesson schedule, etc. For students, the need to obtain the knowledge necessary for professional activity is secondary, since they have a real idea of their future professional activity. are not. Other consumers of university educational services - employers, are primarily interested in the professional knowledge of specialists, for whom the educational process, the nature and methods of providing educational material are in second place.

Accordingly, higher educational institutions aimed at improving the quality of education must ensure that the requirements of all target consumer groups are met, as well as prove that the quality of the educational services provided meets the requirements of consumers.

Quality is a topic for discussion for all interested parties. Each subject must formulate its requirements in the most precise form. The university must be able to combine these various desires and requirements. If possible, the requirements of all disciplines should be translated into the goals and objectives of the educational program. If this is done, then we can talk about (quality of education) at the university. (Fig. 1).

SCHEME FOR FORMING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION

Based on this picture, we can say that the government, employers (higher education and other organizations), teachers and students are the organizers of the educational process. The fact that higher education institutions simultaneously offer two goods, on the one hand, educational services to students, and on the other hand, as a place of delivery of graduates to organizations, leads to the transformation of requirements into the goals and objectives of the educational program.

In accordance with the requirements of international standards in the field of quality systems, services should include characteristics or requirements that can be monitored and evaluated by the consumer.

Control over compliance with state requirements for the content and quality of specialist training is provided by external (in relation to the university) procedures for licensing vocational education programs, certification and accreditation of universities. Specific, professional requirements are controlled and met by the industry certification system. The third subject - the consumer of educational services - the individual's requirements are not documented and are not conveyed to educational institutions, although his "satisfaction" largely determines the quality of his professional training.

Conclusion.

International practice shows that for the effective functioning of higher education, it is necessary to create a Quality System [1]. Unlike State Standards, which determine the level and content of specialist training, the characteristics of the educational process, the Quality System characterizes the actual or desired level of services provided by an educational institution to students. The quality system also allows for the presence of characteristics that are not always observed by the consumer. The main thing is that these characteristics are convenient for assessment by the educational institution itself.

Thus, the purpose of the quality system is to ensure that the declared quality level is guaranteed for consumers of educational services and reliably maintained at the university.

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